

CHANGING PATTERN AND TREND OF LOK SABHA VERDICT IN MAHARASHTRA

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Abstract

Political patterns and trends remain dynamic over the period in Maharashtra since the post-independence era. Still, Lok Sabha election results in Maharashtra have shown significant changes and trends over recent decades, reflecting the developing political landscape of the state. Maharashtra has seen a shift from the traditionally dominated party of the Indian National Congress towards coalition politics and the rise of regional parties like the National Congress party, Shiv Sena. The 2014 Lok Sabha election verdict in Maharashtra marked a major turning point as the Bharatiya Janata Party emerged as the dominant party, and that trend continued into 2019. The 2024 Lok Sabha election verdict highlights a competitive and fragmented political environment. The BJP-led NDA continues to hold significant ground, especially in urban areas, while the opposition INDIA alliance, consisting of the Congress, NCP (Sharad Pawar faction), and Shiv Sena (Uddhav Thackeray faction), remained strong in several constituencies. This political pattern indicates evolving polarization between urban and rural voter bases, as well as regional dynamics playing a crucial role in determining the outcomes of the election. The research also shows the impact of shifting alliances and the importance of regional leaders

in Maharashtra's politics. This paper focuses on the changing patterns and trends of the Maharashtra electoral system from 2009 to 2024. Secondary data has been analyzed by collecting it from various sources. Statistical technique Coefficient of variation (CV) used to measure the relative variability of won seats by UPA, NDA and Others from 2009 to 2024.

Keywords: *political landscape, coalition politics, regional dynamics, electoral trends, political fragmentation*

Introduction

The Indian Lok Sabha elections, the world's largest democratic exercise, have historically reflected the dynamic socio-political landscape of the country; at the same time, the pattern and trend of Lok Sabha verdicts also have evolved significantly over the decades, reflecting changes in political drift, emotional behavior, and socioeconomic factors. The early post-independence era was more influential. In the initial year after independence, the Indian National Congress (INC) was the only dominant political party. It brought the best appeal, and leadership under Jawaharlal Nehru led to considerable electoral victories. The party's strong position was built on a platform of national unification, people's beliefs, and development. Till 1970, INC enjoyed power without any strong opposition. However, the 1970s and 1980s witnessed a decline in Congress's dominance due to various factors, including internal disputes and the rise of national parties. The emergency period (1975–1977) and consequent political instability led to the formation of the Janata party, which won the 1977 elections.

Leaders like Indira Gandhi and the rise of regional parties such as the DMK, AIADMK, and others started to reset the political landscape, raising regional issues and focusing local governance. The emergence of regional parties in the 1990s led to vote fragmentation leading to a shift from single party to coalition politics. The 1991 elections witnessed the end of single-party dominance with the formation of coalition governments. The period was marked by a mix of national and regional parties coming together to form governments. The Bhartiya Janata Party (BJP) started to gain eminence, taking advantage of nationalistic sentiments and economic reforms. Under the leadership of Narendra Modi, the BJP has gained significant electoral success since the 2014 Lok Sabha elections. The party focused on nationalism, economic development, and anti-corruption resonance. The 2014 and 2019 Lok Sabha elections marked a shift from the previous era of coalition politics to a single-party majority government. The BJP showed the ability to change the voter's performances.

Despite the BJP's dominance, other regional parties continue to shape the electoral outcomes, especially in states like West Bengal, Tamil Nadu, and Uttar Pradesh. Regional parties

influence national politics through strategic planning, alliances, and regional strength. The factors included cast, religion, and regional identity, affects voter's behavior and political strategies. Due to the growing influence of young and urban voters, a new dynamic strategy was introduced in politics. Issues like unemployment, education, basic facilities, and urban infrastructure have gained significance. The use of social media and digital platforms has transformed and allowed political parties to reach the voters in a broader manner. Despite the strong leadership of PM Narendra Modi, the 2024 Lok Sabha election proved a setback to the BJP. National politics has always influenced state politics since the post-independence era. Maharashtra State is not exceptional for this, which has undergone notable changes over the years in politics.

After independent, due to the national strength and strong organizational base, the Indian National Congress became the dominant party in Maharashtra under the leadership of Yashwantrao Chavan and Vasant Rao Naik. The shift started to take place with the emergence of regional political parties. Shiv Sena, founded by Bala Saheb Thackeray in 1966, started to challenge the Congress's dominance. Shiv Sena became popular among voters in a short period by focusing on regional identity, Marathi pride, and issues affecting the urban poor and working class. By the 1980s, Shiv Sena became a significant political force in Mumbai and the rest of Maharashtra. It was around 1990 when BJP and Shiv Sena, formed a coalition government, marking a significant shift in Maharashtra's politics. Leaders like Gopinath Munde, Pramod Mahajan, and Narayan Rane played important roles in strengthening the coalition. Despite major obstacles and setbacks in the state the BJP continued to perform well in the national election and had a strong presence in Maharashtra.

The BJP, Shiv Sena, showed dominance in the 2004 state election. In the 2019 state assembly election, the Shiv Sena broke its alliance with the BJP and formed the Maha Vikas Aaghadi (MVA) with the Indian National Congress (INC) and the Nationalist Congress Party (NCP). Uddhav Thackeray of Shiv Sena became chief minister of Maharashtra. Despite major obstacles and setbacks in the state, the BJP continued to perform well in the national election and had a strong presence in Maharashtra. In the last 3 years, Maharashtra state experienced a major quake in the political arena. By rebelling with the Shiv Sena, Eknath Shinde broke the Shiv Sena in 2022 and eventually formed a coalition government with the BJP.

Similarly, Sharad Chandra Pawar's nephew, Ajit Pawar broke the NCP party and joined hands with the BJP. These two major splits between Shiv Sena and NCP have changed the political

landscape in Maharashtra showing its impact on vote bank of 2024 Lok Sabha results of the state. Maharashtra Election verdict has always been faced by various challenges, including caste and identity politics, urban versus rural divide, and economic and social issues. In addition to all these reasons, the verdict of the 2024 Lok Sabha polls is also affected by many other reasons, including misuse of investigation agencies, Maratha reservation issues, frequent splits in political parties, and changing political leadership and power. This changing political pattern and trend and its effect on the 2024 Lok Sabha verdict in Maharashtra are discussed in this paper.

Study Region

Situated near the Arabian coast, Maharashtra lies along the western part of India. It was formed on May 1, 1960. Maharashtra is the third-largest state by area in the country, and the current estimated population of Maharashtra is approximately 13.16 crore as per the 2011 census. The majority of Maharashtra is covered by black soil derived from decomposed lava rocks. The climate is subtropical to tropical with alternative wet and dry seasons. Maharashtra is a politically notable state in India with a complex structure of administrative and electrical divisions. It is divided into six administrative divisions and 48 Lok Sabha constituency. The state has 288 constituencies of Vidhan Sabha. it has a multi-party-political system with national and regional political parties. In 2024, total registered electors were 9,23,56,251 of which male electors constitute 4,80,12,139 and female 4,80,12,139.

Literature review

Ananth V. Krishna, "India Since Independence: Making Sense of Indian Politics," thoroughly analyzed the political developments in India post-1947. Key events like the consolidation of the Indian state, the rise of regional parties, and the emergency period liberalization era are discussed in this book. This book shows how complex political dynamics have shaped its journey as a democratic republic." Nitin Birmal and Suhas Palshikar's "Maharashtra: Towards a New Party System critically analyses the political landscape in Maharashtra. This paper focused on understanding the historical context, political evolution, and the factors influencing the development of a new party system in the state. This paper revolves around the shift from a single-party dominant system to a more fragmented and coalition-driven landscape that reflects broader socioeconomic changes in the state. Suhas Palshikar, a well-known political scientist, examines the major shifts in the Maharashtra political landscape during the 2014 Lok Sabha elections. In the article Maharashtra: Congress-NCP Manages Victory", Rajeshwari

Deshpande studied the political dynamics and strategies that led to the success of the Congress-NCP alliance in the Maharashtra 2009 assembly election. The article discusses electrostatic dynamics in Maharashtra and the significance of coalition politics, emphasizing how the Congress-NCP alliance manages to maintain the United Front. The writer analyses campaign strategies, the crucial role of leadership, voter behavior, and social dynamics, challenges, and criticism. S. Palshikar and K.C. Suri discussed in their article "The 2014 Lok Sabha elections: critical shifts in Long Term, Cautious in the Short Term", the decline of the Congress-NCP alliance and the rise of the BJP-Shiv Sena coalition, signifying these changes to anti-incumbency, effective campaigning, and influence of Narendra Modi. The 2014 election was known as a significant realignment in Maharashtra politics, with urban and semiurban voters strongly favoring the BJP, which led to the shift in power dynamics. In the article "Political crisis in Maharashtra: BJP-backed government in power" Ronojoy Sen focused on the political crisis in Maharashtra, particularly the BJP's bad government's brief tenure as well as the complexities of the Maharashtra post-2019 election scenario. Sen highlighted the breakdown of the BJP Shiv Sena alliance over power-sharing disputes leading to stability in the political landscape of Maharashtra. The researcher critically examined the BJP's political strategies, the role of the government, and the legal challenges that arose, reflecting broader trends of political antibiotics and shifting alliances in Maharashtra.

Objective

- To analyze the voting patterns in Maharashtra for Lok Sabha elections.
- To identify significant changes in voter behavior over different election cycles.
- To explore the socio-political factors influencing these changes

Database and research methodology

To analyze the changing patterns and trends of the Lok Sabha verdict, the researcher used secondary data as well as a simple approach involving descriptive statistics and trend analysis. Secondary data sources, such as past election results, voter turnout records, demographic data from the census, and reports from the Election Commission of India, provided a foundation for this research. By examining these sources, researchers used descriptive statistics, like percentages and averages, to understand vote share, seat distributions, and voter turnout over different election cycles. For analyze the changing pattern over time, data from 4 general elections from 2009 to 2024 was used and Statistical technique, Coefficient of variation (CV) was employed to measure the relative variability or consistency of won seats by UPA, NDA, and Others from 2009 to 2024.

Results and discussion.

2009 Lok Sabha General Election verdict in Maharashtra

Maharashtra, one of the largest states, plays an important role in Indian politics with 28 Lok Sabha seats, making it the second-largest state in terms of parliamentary representation. The 2009 Lok Sabha elections in Maharashtra saw some significant changes in voting patterns and a dynamic trend compared to previous elections.

Table 1: Lok Sabha General Election Result in Maharashtra (2004-2009)

Party	Seats won (2004)	Seats won (2009)	Change in seats	Vote share (%) 2004	Vote share (%) 2009	Change in vote share (%)
INC	13	17	+4	22.71	19.6	-3.08
NCP	09	08	-1	16.09	19.28	-1.97
SS	12	11	-1	20.60	17.00	-3.38
BJP	13	09	-4	22.56	18.17	-3.74
Others	01	03	+2	18.04	25.95	+12.17

By observing the table, the INC gained 4 seats, increasing its total from 13 to 17, while the NCP lost 1 seat. Both parties experienced a decrease in their overall vote share compared to 2004. The BJP and Shiv Sena lost their seats in this election. The BJP lost by 4 seats, and Shiv Sena decreased by 1 seat. Both parties declined in their vote share. While other parties, saw a significant increase in both the number of seats won (from 1 to 3) and their total vote share, which increased by 12.17%.

Source: Generated by Author.

Party performance in various political divisions of Maharashtra**Table 2: Votes won by political parties (Lok Sabha Election 2009)**

Division	INC	NCP	BJP	Shiv Sena	Others
Konkan	02	01	00	03	01
Mumbai	05	01	00	00	00
Western Maharashtra	03	03	01	02	02
North Maharashtra	01	01	04	00	00
Vidarbha	04	01	02	03	00
Marathwada	02	01	02	03	00
Total	17	08	09	11	03

The 2009 Lok Sabha election verdict showed the various significant changes in the political landscape of Maharashtra. National party strategies and their coalitions with regional parties significantly impacted the outcomes of the election. The INC emerged as the leading political party in Maharashtra, gaining a total of 17 seats. The party performed well across all regions, with significant victories in Mumbai, Western Maharashtra, Vidarbha, and Marathwada. The NCP won 8 seats with a strong performance in Western Maharashtra. The BJP also secured 9 seats with significant victories in North Maharashtra and a presence in other divisions except Konkan and Mumbai. Shiv Sena managed to win the second-highest 11 seats, dominating the Konkan, Marathwada, and Vidarbha regions, and other parties managed to be 3 seats in the Konkan and Western Maharashtra divisions 1 and 2, respectively.

2014 Lok Sabha General Election verdict in Maharashtra.

Significant change was experienced in the 2014 Lok Sabha of Maharashtra politics. The 2014 Lok Sabha elections in Maharashtra were significant for several reasons. Bhartiya Janata Party (BJP) made a dramatic increase in its number of seats by winning 23 out of 48 constituencies in Maharashtra, just from 9 in 2009. The rise of the BJP was largely attributed to the national wave of support for Narendra Modi, and the party's focus on development and anti-corruption as well as modern India. The Shiv Sena also saw an increase in its seat count by securing 18 seats from 11 in 2009. This victory was partly due to its strategic alliance with the BJP, which held consolidated votes and strengthened their overall performance in Maharashtra. The Congress party experienced a notable decline in both shares and seats. They could manage to win only 12 seats compared to 17 in 2009. It was a reflection of widespread dissatisfaction with the UPA government and its performance. The Nationalist Congress Party (NCP) also experienced a decline as it won 7 seats, down from 8 in 2009.

Table 3: Lok Sabha General Election Result in Maharashtra (2009-2014)

Party	Seats won (2009)	Seats won (2014)	Change in seats	Vote share (%) 2009	Vote share (%) 2014	Change in vote share (%)
INC	17	12	-5	19.6	18.13	-1.47
NCP	08	07	-1	19.28	15.97	-3.41
SS	11	18	+7	17.00	20.63	+3.63
BJP	09	23	+14	18.17	27.37	+9.2
MNS	00	01	+1	00.00	1.45	+1.45
Others	00	00	00	25.95	16.45	-9.5

Source: Generated by Author.

Party performance in various political divisions of Maharashtra in 2014

The BJP emerged as a dominant party by securing the highest 23 seats in all political divisions of Maharashtra. Following the BJP, Shiv Sena won second highest by winning 18 seats. The Party performed significantly in the Konkan division by winning 5 seats, in Vidarbha, 4 seats, and in Marathwada and Mumbai, 3 seats, respectively. NCP managed to win all 4 seats in western Maharashtra only. Except for 2 seats in Marathwada, INC. could not secure any seat in any division. Others won 1 seat, and that is in western Maharashtra only.

Table 4: Votes won by political parties (Lok Sabha Election 2014)

Division	INC	NCP	BJP	Shiv Sena	Others
Konkan	00	00	02	05	00
Mumbai	00	00	03	03	00
Western Maharashtra	00	04	04	02	01
North Maharashtra	00	00	05	01	00
Vidarbha	00	00	06	04	00
Marathwada	02	00	03	03	00
Total	02	04	23	18	01

The impact of the Narendra Modi wave and the BJP's campaign strategy played a crucial role in shaping the outcome and influenced not only the national but also the state-level results. The successful alliance between the BJP and the Shiv Sena has shown the importance of coalition politics in achieving electoral success. The complete anti-Congress wave pushed the Congress-led UPA government to the brink of defeat. The BJP's planned electoral strategy, including highlighting issues such as governance, development, and anti-corruption, connected well with the electorate and contributed to their significant victories.

2019 Lok Sabha General Election Verdict in Maharashtra

The 2019 general election in Maharashtra, influenced by various factors that affected the seats won by major parties, led to a change in the pattern of the political arena in Maharashtra.

Table 5: Lok Sabha General Election Result in Maharashtra (2014-2019)

Party	Seats won (2014)	Seats won (2019)	Change in seats	Vote share (%) 2014	Vote share (%) 2019	Change in vote share (%)
INC	02	01	-1	18.12	16.11	-2.01
NCP	04	04	00	16.11	15.48	-0.63
SS	18	18	00	20.82	23.5	+2.76
BJP	23	23	00	27.57	27.84	+0.28
Others	01	02	+1	17.39	17.02	-0.37

The BJP and Shiv Sena, contested together as a part of the National Democratic Alliance (NDA), continued their hold on Maharashtra by winning a combined total of 41 out of 48 seats in both the 2014 and 2019 Lok Sabha general elections. This indicated the continuous support of voters for the NDA coalition in the state. Shiv Sena slightly increased their vote share by 2.76%, while the BJP's share increased by 0.28%. The Indian National Congress (INC) and Nationalist Congress Party (NCP), ally groups in the United Progressive Alliance (UPA), did not perform well in this election. The Indian National Congress seat count decreased from 2 in 2014 to 1 in 2019, and its vote share also decreased by 2.01%. The number of seats won by other parties and independent candidates slightly increased from 1 in 2014 to 2 in 2019. Their overall vote share is slightly increased.

Source: Generated by Author.

Table 6: Vote won by political parties (Lok Sabha Election 2019)

Division	INC	NCP	BJP	Shiv Sena	Others
Konkan	00	01	01	05	00
Mumbai	00	00	03	03	00
Western Maharashtra	00	03	05	03	00
North Maharashtra	00	00	05	01	00
Vidarbha	01	00	05	03	01
Marathwada	00	00	04	03	01
Total	01	04	23	18	02

As in the 2014 elections, the BJP performed remarkably well in the 2019 elections, winning a maximum of 23 seats with significant performance across all political divisions in Maharashtra except Konkan, where it won only 1 seat. Following that, Shiv Sena performed significantly in Konkan and won 5 seats and also won 3 seats in Mumbai West, Maharashtra, Vidarbha, and Marathwada, respectively. The NCP fared poorly, winning a total of 4 seats 3 of them only in Western Maharashtra, and the Congress won only 1 seat, which was in Vidarbha. Others got a total of 2 seats, 1 each in Vidarbha and Marathwada.

Several significant factors influenced the 2019 Lok Sabha election in Maharashtra. A strong alliance between the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) and the Shiv Sena under the National Democratic Alliance (NDA) played a very important role in their electoral success. Despite some disputes between the two parties over seat sharing and other issues, they managed to

present a united front that resonated with the voters. On the other hand, the Indian National Congress (INC) and the Nationalist Congress Party (NCP) contested as allies under the United Progressive Alliance (UPA). But this struggle with a lack of coordination failed to challenge the BJP-Shiv Sena combine. Besides all these factors, the popularity of Prime Minister Narendra Modi as a strong and decisive leader was a significant factor in the BJP's performance across India, including Maharashtra. The government's nationalistic policies and development agenda appealed to a large section of the voters. Issues raised by the BJP, such as national security, economic growth, and corruption-free government over local original concerns, worked in favor of the BJP. An impactful implementation of various welfare schemes by the central government, such as the Pradhan Mantri Kisan Samman Nidhi (PM-KISAN), the Ujjwala Yojana, the Swachh Bharat Mission, and others, helped to attract voters, specifically those from rural and lower-income backgrounds. In contrast, the Congress and NCP had a lack of leadership and vision to counter the BJP's agenda, as well as a lack of coordination within the Congress and NCP and other smaller parties, which weakened their ability to present a united front that could not propose the strong challenge against the ruling alliance. The Maratha community, which constitutes a significant portion of the state population, agitated and demanded reservation, but the BJP and Shiv Sena managed to navigate their issues without losing their support. The BJP's effective use of social media and digital platforms to reach voters, particularly the youth, played an important role in shaping public opinion. The BJP and Shiv Sena's grassroots campaigning, including the rally's door-to-door visit and mobilization, ensured a higher turnout and support of voters.

2024 Lok Sabha Election Verdict in Maharashtra

The verdict of the 2024 Lok Sabha general election in Maharashtra was a major setback for the BJP. The BJP decreased in both seats won and vote share in 2024 compared to 2019. Long instability and dramatic change in the political landscape of Maharashtra influenced the result of the general election significantly. BJP, by losing 14 seats in a 2024 general election, won only 9 seats. After the split in Shiv Sena, Uddhav Thackeray-led Shiv Sena won 9 seats, while Eknath Shinde led Shiv Sena won 7 seats and secured a 12.95% vote share. NCP led by Ajit Pawar won 1 seat, while NCP led by Sharad Pawar won 8 seats. The Indian National Congress won 13 seats, increasing by 12 seats, compared to 2019 general election. Although the Indian National Congress won the most seats in the 2024 elections, the BJP's vote share (26.18%)

exceeded the INC's vote share (16.92%) despite losing 14 seats compared to the previous election.

Table 7: Lok Sabha Election Result in Maharashtra (2019-2024)

Party	Seats won (2019)	Seats won (2024)	Change in seats	Vote share (%) 2019	Vote share (%) 2024	Change in vote share (%)
INC	01	13	+12	16.41	16.92	+0.51
NCP (SP)	New	08	+8	-	10.27	10.27
Shiv Sena (UBT)	New	09	+9	-	16.52	16.52
BJP	23	09	-14	27.84	26.18	-1.66
NCP (AP)	04	01	-3	15.66	3.60	-12.06
Shiv Sena	18	07	-11	23.5	12.95	-10.55

Source: Generated by Author.

Internal splits and changes in alliances impacted the verdict of the election. The Indian National Congress and Nationalist Congress Party, led by Sharad Pawar, improved their seat count and vote share with strategic alliances and planning. Taking advantage of the dissatisfaction of the voters against the ruling party, the opposite party turned the voters in favor of them; the performances of smaller parties and independent candidates improved, which showed diversification in voter performances.

Table 8: Vote won by political parties (Lok Sabha Election 2024)

Division	INC	NCP (SP)	Shiv Sena (UBT)	BJP	Shiv Sena (ES)	NCP (AP)	Others
Konkan	00	01	00	02	02	01	00
Mumbai	01	00	03	01	01	00	00
Western Maharashtra	02	04	00	02	02	00	01
North Maharashtra	02	01	01	02	00	00	00
Vidarbha	05	01	01	02	01	00	00
Marathwada	03	01	04	00	01	00	00
Total	13	08	09	09	07	01	01

After the split between Shiv Sena and the NCP, there was a drastic change in the number of seats won by various parties in various political constituencies. With significant performances in Vidarbha (5 seats) and Marathwada (3 seats), INC emerged as the largest party, winning 13 seats. Congress won seats in all the divisions except Konkan. Shiv Sena (UBT) won a total of 9 seats after the bifurcation, out of which 4 in Marathwada and 3 in Mumbai. The Sharad Pawar-led NCP bagged a total of 8 seats, 4 of which were won in West Maharashtra and 1 seat each in all divisions except Mumbai. The BJP won a total of 9 seats, while Shiv Sena led by Eknath Shinde, won a total of 7 seats.

The most significant factor in the 2024 election was the realignment of alliances. The split within the Shiv Sena, with factions led by Uddhav Thackeray and Eknath Shinde, as well as the split within the Nationalist Congress Party, with factions led by Sharad Pawar and Ajit Pawar, created massive change in the political arena in Maharashtra. Local issues like farmer distress, unemployment, infrastructure development and Anti-incumbency sentiments against the ruling coalition government influenced voter behavior, especially in rural areas. BJP's emphasis on Hindutva led the Muslim community and other minorities to turn towards Congress. Effective use of social media, powerful campaign strategies, impactful leadership development promises, and textual attacks on opposition shape the electronic verdict.

Analysis

Following line graph showing the number of seats won by UPA, NDA, and Others in the Maharashtra Lok Sabha elections from 2009 to 2024. The graph reflects the performance of each alliance over the 4 election cycles.

In 2009 UPA shown a strong presence in Maharashtra but in a 2014 and 2019 there was a significant decline in UPA’s performance due to various factors including anti-incumbency, corruption allegations, appeal of NDA’s leadership, lack of a compiling local leadership and campaign strategy. In contrast, NDA made remarkable leap in a 2014, particularly under Narendra Modi's popularity. But in a 2024 NDA dramatically lost their support and UPA (in 2024 INDIA) shown the strong performance and made remarkable leap by winning 30 seats. There was a clear and significant shift toward the NDA in Maharashtra from 2014 to 2019 but in a 2024 it again shifted towards the UPA (INDIA).

To analyse the variability in the number of won seats by UPA, NDA, and Others in Maharashtra Lok Sabha elections from 2009 to 2024 using the coefficient of variation (CV), researcher first needed to calculate the standard deviation (SD) and mean for each group. The coefficient of variation is a major of relative variability, which is calculated as:

$$C.V. = \frac{\sigma}{\bar{x}} \times 100$$

Where C.V. = Coefficient of Variation

σ = Standard Deviation

\bar{x} = Mean

(Note: Higher the CV indicates greater dispersion)

UPA’s CV 67.58% indicating high level of variability in the number of seats won by the UPA across the elections. This high CV suggesting that the UPA’s performance has been quite inconsistent. Large fluctuations are taken place in the voter support. NDA’s 37.98% CV indicating moderate variability in the won number of seats. This suggests a more consistent

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performance compare to the UPA, but still with some degree of fluctuation. The moderate CV indicates that the NDA has managed to maintain a relatively steady level of support in Maharashtra over the election cycles but with some fluctuations. On the other hand, Other parties shows 47.37% CV representing moderate to high variability. This indicates that the performance of Others varies quite a bit from one election to another.

Conclusion

The changing patterns and trends of the Lok Sabha verdict in Maharashtra up to 2024 reveal a developing and dynamic political scenario. Traditionally, the Maharashtra political landscape was dominated by the Indian National Congress and the Nationalist Congress Party. However, over the past decade, there has been a significant shift towards the BJP and Shiv Sena alliance, mainly since the 2014 Lok Sabha election. The BJP's emergence has been driven by factors such as affective grassroots organization, strong and effective leadership, and a focus on development and national security that influence the voters in favor of the BJP. The 2019 elections further strengthened the BJP's presence in Maharashtra in spite of Shiv Sena breaking out of the BJP post-elections to form a government with the INC and NCP in the state assembly, reflecting the fluidity of alliances. By the 2024 elections, the political landscape of Maharashtra became more fragmented with emerging regional parties and coalitions. This shift indicated a growing diversification of political preferences among the electorate, influenced by local grassroots issues, caste and religion dynamics, urban-rural divides, and the changing social and economic landscape of Maharashtra.

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